

Zambia CLEWs Nexus Working Paper - Annex 2

	Scope/Aims	Climate	Land	Energy	Water
Sectoral Policies					
Water policy (2010)	To optimally harness water resources for the efficient and sustainable utilization of this natural resource to enhance economic productivity and reduce poverty.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Recognises climate change as a big threat to sustainable development. ▪ Notes the increased incidences of droughts and floods. ▪ Calls for assessment and monitoring of potential impacts of climate change on ecosystems. ▪ Advocates for strengthened national climate meteorological databases and monitoring networks. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Advocates for the use of land-use data and information for water resource planning and decision making. ▪ Advocates for integrated land and water resources management. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Considers water as key input resource in energy generation ▪ Accounts for Covers water allocation as vital input for Hydropower generation. For instance, it was projected that a total of 1,200 m3/s of water was expected to be used to generate to 2,380 MW electricity in 2015. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Recognises that water availability is constrained by climate change. ▪ Recognizes a synergy between water and socio-economic development as well as underscoring the resource as vital in food, livestock, energy and aquatic life production.
National Energy Plan (2019)	To achieve an optimal energy resource utilization to meet Zambia's domestic and non-domestic needs at the lowest total economic, financial, social, environmental and opportunity cost and establish Zambia as a net exporter of energy.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Indicates that climate change has negative impacts on hydropower generation. • Confirms that wood fuel is most widely used fuel for cooking and that unsustainable harvest and use exceeds re-growth of biomass. This contributes to climate change and negative health effects. • Advocates for increased systematic mainstreaming 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Underscores the working relationship with line ministries for provision of land rights permits for energy projects and wood fuel regulations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Promotes increased exploitation of renewable energy to diversify the energy mix. ▪ Promotes wider usage of renewable energy technologies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Confirms the existence of synergy between line ministry responsible for water allocation permits and environmental impacts assessment for energy projects.

		of climate change in the energy sector.			
Land policy (2021)	To deliver a transparent land administration and management system for inclusive sustainable development by the year 2035.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifies climate change as a driver that renders land unsuitable for certain land uses due to degradation. • Underscores a relationship between property rights or tenure with how land and natural resources are accessed and managed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Points out weakness and inadequacy of legal framework as reasons for failure to facilitate ownership of land rights, servicing and management. • Recognises lack of integrated land planning in customary land as a challenge. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Does not cover energy</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognises the impacts of reduced rainfall and water availability on agricultural production.
Integrated Resource Plan for the Power Sector (2023)	To provide a comprehensive, forward-looking least cost plan for the development of the country's power sector, including both on-grid and off-grid.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Highlights direct damage implications of increased extreme climate events such as flooding, landslides or wildfires that on infrastructures. ▪ Projects that emissions from coal will increase 5.9 million tonnes/yr as thermal capacity increases to approximately 1,616 MW. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Notes that poorly-planned and poorly-located renewable energy projects may threaten the nation's biodiversity and contribute to local conflicts, impeding progress in grid transformation and climate change mitigation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Accounts for increased uptake of renewable energy. For example, the policy expects energy generation from Biomass, Solar PV and Wind renewables to reach 320MW, 2,083 MW and 1,192 MW by 2030, respectively. ▪ Recognises that the hydropower sector is subjected to significant climate change impacts. ▪ Indicates that Increasing temperatures are expected to increase overall cooling demand. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Indicates a decline in available water for hydropower and other uses. ▪ States that water availability and shifts in rainfall patterns may increase energy requirements for water transfers.

<p>National Forestry Policy (2014)</p>	<p>To manage the nation's forest resources in a sustainable manner to facilitate retention of their ecological integrity and maximize benefits to the nation, especially forest dependent communities.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Recognizes forests as carbon storehouses that play an important function in influencing climate and that the unsustainable and destructive use of forests (i.e. wood fuel production, excessive and increasing forest conversion to cropland) can therefore add to the problem of climate change. ▪ Promotes intervention strategies required to mitigate the effects of climate change. E.g Ensuring sensitization amongst stakeholders of the effects arising from forest products utilization and management. ▪ Promotes measures to improve deforested and degraded forest land. E.g promoting the establishment of plantation forests and encouraging the regeneration of degraded areas. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Notes that 66.4% of Zambia's total land area is covered by forests with 8 percent being covered by other wooded land types; translating into approximately 49.97 and 6.1 million hectares respectively. ▪ Reveals that the Integrated Land Use Assessments (ILUA) undertaken from 2005 to 2008 revealed that 63 percent of forest land is relatively undisturbed or slightly disturbed, 26 percent moderately disturbed and 5.6 percent of forest is considerably disturbed. ▪ Advocates for the establishment of an appropriate incentive framework for investors in forest plantation development and management that include land availability and security of tenure for projects that respond to the national 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Recognizes wood fuel as the largest source of energy in Zambia and that that an estimated 88% of households depend on forests to meet their basic energy Requirements. ▪ Calls for development and use of energy efficient stoves to reduce forest biomass driven (GHG) emissions. ▪ Advocates for the establishment of an incentive system for the expansion of small-scale entrepreneurs manufacturing energy saving cooking braziers and stoves (i.e. consuming limited quantities of charcoal. ▪ Promotes the utilization of wood waste to generate energy such as bio-gasifiers and charcoal briquettes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Associates deforestation as a major factor in soil erosion, siltation of lakes, rivers, dams and other water bodies. ▪ Recognize the promotion of land-use system that ensures the protection of headwaters, river basins and terrestrial resources.
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			<p>sustainable development criteria.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Calls for sufficient and sustainable allocation of land between major competing uses and sectors such as agriculture, energy and mining. 		
National Infrastructure Policy (2023)	To provide adequate, affordable, and quality infrastructure in a timely manner for sustained socio-economic development of the country.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Recognizes the effects of climate change on Infrastructure. ▪ Calls for development of climate resilient infrastructure. ▪ Calls for strengthened infrastructure, disaster risk mitigation and recovery mechanism. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Recognizes lands ministry and local government as responsible for land use planning. ▪ Promotes integration of infrastructure development in natural environments. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Recognizes the need to account for green and energy efficient infrastructure. ▪ Promotes development of energy and climate resilient infrastructure. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Recognizes water as a resource for transport infrastructure. ▪ Accounts for domestic and sanitation water use.
Cross sector Policies					
National Policy on Climate Change (2016)	To provide a framework for coordinating climate change programmes in order to ensure climate resilient and low carbon development pathways for sustainable development towards the attainment of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Discusses the impacts of climate change such as droughts and rising temperatures to as drivers to gradual drying up of biomass. ▪ Calls for efforts to increase resilience of infrastructure, ecosystems and promote innovation, knowledge and education. ▪ Promotes use of financial instruments such as weather-indexed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Accounts sustainable land use planning to protect key ecosystems and related services such as carbon sinks. ▪ Draws emphasis to soil conservation ▪ refers to Land Act Cap 184 as a legal instrument responsible for the management and administration of land in Zambia. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Promotes the scaling up of alternative energy sources, energy efficiency and conservation. ▪ Uses Energy Regulations Act No. 23 of 2003 as legal instrument to address energy tied issues. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Uses Water Resources Management Act No. 21 of 2011 as legal instrument to account for water related issues ▪ Notes the impacts of climate change on ecosystems such as reduced flows and drying up of water bodies.

	Zambia's Vision 2030.	insurance, carbon instruments and catastrophic bonds to enhance resilience and cover climate related risks.			
8th National Development Plan (2022)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To promote socioeconomic transformation for improved livelihoods through economic and job creation, human and social development, environmental sustainability, and good government environment. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indicates that Climate change and increased variability has led to droughts, floods and extreme temperatures on key sectors including energy, agriculture and water. Calls for enhanced climate change mitigation and promotion of low carbon development in line with the NDC. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Calls for full operationalization of Land Policy to address Sustainable land and forest management, Urban and land use planning. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Calls for energy transition to green and renewable energy sources; increasing energy use efficiency, reducing electricity transmission and distribution losses from the national grid. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recognises the link between droughts and high temperatures to reduced water availability and decreased hydroelectricity generation capacity. Reveals government intentions to implement climate resilient water supply infrastructure development and maintenance, water quality monitoring and protection of aquifers and protected water sources.
Nationally Determined Contribution (2023)	To achieve an estimated total GHG emission reduction of 38,000 GgCO ₂ eq which translates to	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identifies the practice of Sustainable agriculture, Sustainable Forest management, deployment of Renewable Energy and energy efficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reports commitments towards emissions reduction with AFOLU interventions estimated at 1,232Gg CO₂ eq. by 2030. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expects the uptake of renewable energy to increase to 10% from 3%. Indicates the planned addition of 1,400MW 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Calls for protection of water aquifer and other water resources.

	47 percent with substantial international support, compared to 20,000 GgCO ₂ eq which translates to 25 percent, under domestic efforts with limited international support, against 2010 as a base year.	technologies as mitigation measures for GHG emissions reduction. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Indicates an estimated 8,370Gg CO₂ eq. emissions reduction to be achieved from renewable energy interventions by 2030. ▪ Advocates for enhanced early warning systems in key sectors for timely actions. 		low carbon hydropower electricity supplied into the grid and facilitation of mass deployment of energy efficient technologies.	
National Adaptation Plan (2023)	To reduce vulnerability, enhancing adaptive capacity, building resilience, and ensuring sustainable development in the face of climate change.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Recognises that climate change poses significant risks to the country's natural resources, socio-economic development, and livelihoods. ▪ Recognizes the need to enhance early warning Systems, up-scaling on dissemination of climate services. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Notes concerns over degradation of farm lands, soils and conservation structures without mentioning interventions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Promotes provision of alternative sources of energy. ▪ Bemoans lack of capacity to integrated alternative energy sources and climate resilient construction codes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Advocates for enhanced climate proofing as an adaptation measure for water infrastructure. ▪ Advocates for Integrate landscape approaches in land use planning in river catchments.
National Green Growth Strategy (2023)	To promote development pathways that lead to Zambia's transition to a low carbon, resource efficient, resilient and socially	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Confirms that climate change is becoming more visible as evidenced in the mean annual temperatures that have increased by 1.3 CO while the mean annual precipitation has 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Recognises that Zambia's Economic growth has been attained using the resources sub-optimally as evidenced by the extremely low agricultural land 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Calls for energy demand to be electrified step by step to phase out fossil fuels and reduce deforestation by shrinking the use of biomass for energy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Recognises that water resources are vulnerable to climate change. ▪ Notes that dry weather and droughts are significantly

	<p>inclusive economy by 2030.</p>	<p>been decreasing at an average rate of 1.9mm per month since 1960.</p>	<p>productivity and water use efficiency. Calls for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Reduced land degradation and restoration of degraded areas. ▪ Promotes sustainable land conversion ▪ Protection of ecologically sensitive areas; and ▪ Promotion and enforcement of land zoning. 		<p>impairing the availability of water for domestic use such as agriculture with substantial part of annual crop production being lost and communities made food insecure due to water scarcity and intensified dry periods during the rainy season.</p>
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